

Studies in the Kinetics of the Coagulation of Colloids. Part V. The Variation of Viscosity during Coagulation.

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The work of Miyazawa (*J. Chem. Soc.*, Japan, 1912, **33**, 1179), Freundlich and Ishizaka (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1913, **9**, 66), Wo. Ostwald (*ibid.*, p. 34), Pauli (*ibid.*, p. 64), Gann (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1916, **8**, 65), Smoluchowski (*Kolloid Z.*, 1916, **18**, 190), and numerous other workers, has shown the marked utility of viscometric observations in the kinetic studies of coagulations. The interesting work, especially of Freundlich (*loc. cit.*, cf. also Freundlich, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry, Eng. Trans., 1926) and of Gann (*loc. cit.*), has been the chief and earliest evidence for *autocatalysis* in the coagulation of colloids. Evidence was, however, adduced in the previous papers in this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 11, 337; 1932, **9**, 157, and especially the *P. C. Rây Commemoration Volume of Indian Chem. Soc.*, pp. 41-52) to show that though prevalent under certain conditions, *autocatalysis* can not be considered as a general characteristic of the coagulation phenomenon. It is also of interest to observe that practically all the systematic work on the viscometric examination of the kinetics of coagulation is restricted to lyophilic sols. The following work was, therefore, undertaken to extend the above line of work to lyophobic, and especially to examine what support can be given to the view mentioned above regarding the nature of the coagulation process. This has been studied here in the case of arsenious sulphide and gelatine and their mixtures when coagulated by differently concentrated solutions of potassium chloride.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A review of the literature shows that practically all the previous work on the viscometric examination of the kinetics of coagulation

was carried out by the use of the Ostwald's viscometer. This requires a knowledge of the transpiration time of the liquid and the corresponding density. Now the measurement of the last quantity is rather inconvenient in the case of a coagulating sol. Unfortunately, this determination is absent in the majority of papers on the viscosity changes of coagulating sols, which detracts at any rate from the precision of the interpretation of the viscosity term applied to such data. A convenient method in such cases is the one due to Scarpa (*Gazzetta*, 1910, 40, 271; cf. also Farrow, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 347); this does not necessitate a knowledge of the density of the liquid. This method was, therefore, adopted with modifications, described in the sequel, which add appreciably to the precision of

FIG. A.

measurement. A suitable quantity of water from the aspirator A_1 was let out in B (Fig. A). The pressure diminution thus produced is observed on the manometer M , and communicated to the pipette P by opening the tap T_1 , T_2 being closed. t_1 , the time for the liquid to rise between two marks made on P under this suction was noted. T_1 is then closed and T_2 opened. This connects P with the atmosphere through a quantity of glass wool, kept at W in order to avoid dust, etc.,

from entering the apparatus; the liquid in P therefore begins to fall. This time t_2 similar to t_1 is noted, η the viscosity is then given by

$$\eta = K \cdot \frac{t_1 \cdot t_2}{t_1 + t_2}$$

where K , a constant, is determined from a knowledge of t_1 and t_2 for a liquid like water for which η (0.7225 centipoise at 35°) is known. The aspirator A_1 connected with A_2 is rather convenient in order to replenish water in the latter. The use of stop-cocks T_1 and T_2 well lubricated with good vacuum grease, instead of pinch cocks, added greatly to the reproducibility of results, and specially to an accurate adjustment of the pressure in A_1 , prior to the observation of t_1 . This precaution appears to have been neglected by previous workers.

Majority of the experiments were made with the arsenious sulphide sol. It was prepared, and its colloid content determined, as described in Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 11). The last quantity in all the experiments (except those to which Fig. 5 refers) was 4.5 g. of As_2S_3 per litre in the coagulating mixture. Coagulations were also studied where the above colloid was protected by different concentrations of gelatine solutions. These were prepared by soaking in distilled water weighed pieces of gelatine cut from pure sheet. 20 C.c. of the colloid and 10 c.c. of one of the gelatine solutions were mixed and allowed to stand for 15 minutes. To the mixture was then added 10 c.c. from variously concentrated solutions of potassium chloride and the viscosity determined at successive intervals during the progress of coagulation. These results have been shown graphically in Figs. 3 and 4 (*cf.* also Tables III and IV). Figs. 1, 2 and 5 (also Tables I, II and V) refer respectively to viscosity variations when only the arsenious sulphide sol, and gelatine solutions were mixed with solutions of potassium chloride. The temperature of the thermostat was maintained at 35° in all the experiments. Stirring was discontinued during observations of t_1 and t_2 . Concentrations of the electrolyte added were such as to have the coagulation prolonged over a fairly wide time period. Observations of viscosity were discontinued as soon as flocculation (that is, the formation of just visible heterogeneities consisting of coagulated particles tending to deposit a fine film on the inside of the pipette P in Fig. A) sets in. During the course of this work it was observed that immediately after the

start of the coagulation, the viscosity—coagulation time curve almost always showed a minimum. Since this phenomenon does not appear to have been studied previously, it has been investigated here in some detail. The data given in Tables I—IV were read off the corresponding curves in Figs. 1—5. Fig. 6 relates the coagulator concentration with the time interval up to the attainment of the first minimum mentioned above from the start of coagulation.

TABLE I (cf Fig 1).

Colloid used = $As_2 S_3$.

Reference.	KCl conc.	Initial viscosity.	First minimum viscosity.	Time corresponding to η_m in mins.	Viscosity diminution in per cent.	Final observed viscosity.	Time corresponding to η_f in mins.	Remarks.
Curve No.		η_i	η_m			η_f		
1	N/16	0.744	0.732	13	1.6	1.27	130	Flocculation commenced after this
2	N/16.6	0.744	0.732	11	1.6	0.98	136	Do
3	N/17.4	0.737	0.727	11	1.4	1.60	185	

TABLE II (cf. Fig. 2).

Colloid used = $As_2 S_3$.

4	N/17.7	0.743	0.729	19	1.9	0.752	180	No flocculation ; η , after 24 hrs. 0.789
5	N/18.2	0.738	0.727	27	1.5	0.805	225	No flocculation ; η , after 24 hrs. 0.839
6	N/19	0.737	0.723	28	1.8	0.731	218	No flocculation ; η , after 24 hrs. 0.752
7	N/20	0.737	0.732	25	0.7	0.742	245	No flocculation ; η , after 24 hrs. 0.839

TABLE III.

Colloid used = As_2S_3 protected by 0.25% gelatine.

Reference.	KCl conc.	Initial viscosity.	First minimum viscosity.	Time corresponding to η_m .	Viscosity diminution in per cent.	Final observed viscosity.	Time corresponding to η_f .	Remarks.
Curve No.		η_i	η_m			η_f		
8	N/10	0.748	—	—	—	0.838	44	Flocculation just perceptible after about 50 mins.
9	N/11.1	0.750	0.739	10	1.5	0.875	400	No flocculation ; after 20 hrs. 1.11
10	N/11.4	0.746	0.738	11	1.1	1.28	230	Flocculation just perceptible after 23 hrs. after 23 hrs. 2.58
11	N/11.7	0.745	0.739	10	0.8	1.19	300	No flocculation
12	N/12.5	0.743	0.738	11	0.7	0.758	166	Do
13	N/13.3	0.785	0.779	11	0.8	0.958	180	Do

TABLE IV (cf. Fig. 4).

Colloid used = As_2S_3 protected by 0.05% gelatine.

14	N/10	0.779	0.766	11	1.7	0.767	125	No Flocculation. η rises to 0.847 after 24 hours
15	N/13.3	0.755	0.741	12	1.9	0.743	251	No flocculation ; η becomes practically constant

TABLE V.

16	N	0.754	0.749	12	0.7	0.748	—	η fluctuates about a mean values after initial fall
17	N/2	0.751	0.749	12	1.2	—	—	
18	N/2	0.738	0.729	25	1.2	—	—	Do

Nos. 16 and 17 refer to As_2S_3 sol protected by 0.1% gelatine and No. 18 by 0.05% gelatine.

DISCUSSION.

These results show that the rise of viscosity during the period observed diminishes rapidly, *e.g.*, from about 70% in 130 minutes to about 1% in over 200 minutes, as the concentration of the coag.

gulator is reduced from $N/16$ to $N/20$ (cf. Tables I, II; curves 1, 7, Figs. 1 and 2). This result is in agreement with the known profound influence of changes in the concentration of the coagulator upon the rate of coagulation in the region of the *slow coagulation*. Although sufficiently numerous and strictly comparable data are not available it would appear that lyophilic sols do not show so great a sensitivity to changes in the concentration of the coagulator. This deduction is supported by the results of Freundlich and Ishizaka (*loc. cit.*) for the coagulation of such a typical lyophilic sol as aluminium hydroxide produced by potassium salicylate solutions in the range, 5 to 10 millimols per litre, and also those obtained in this work (cf. Tables III, IV).

FIG. 1.

The coagulator conc. for curves 1, 2, 3 were $N/16$, $N/16.6$, $N/17.4\text{-KCl}$ respectively.

FIG. 2.

The coagulator conc. for curves 4, 5, 6 and 7 were $N/17.7$, $N/18.2$, $N/19$ and $N/20\text{-KCl}$ respectively.

It is interesting to note from curves 1—5 in Figs. 1 and 2 that soon after a small initial fall, the viscosity increases markedly after an appreciable period of a comparatively marked low rate of changes. Assuming tentatively that in the main, viscosity and coagulation change together and in the same sense, this might be ascribed to autocatalysis which ordinarily is the acceleration of the rate of a chemical reaction by the accumulation of the products of the reaction. Its mechanism in the present type of changes is generally considered to be the coagulum particles serving as nuclei for further coagulation. These

FIG. 3.

The colloid was protected by 0.025% gelatine sol. The coagulator conc. for curves 8, 9, 10, 12 and 13 were $N/10$, $N/11.1$, $N/11.4$, $N/12.5$ and $N/13.3$ -KCl respectively.

curves also show that the period after which the coagulation rate becomes large, tends to increase as the concentration of the coagulator is diminished. At still higher dilutions (cf. curve 4, and also curves 6, 7, Fig. 2) the above period would appear to cover practically the entire time of observation; the final value of viscosity in these

coagulations is but slightly higher than the initial one. This slow rising section of the curve is not so conspicuous in most of the coagulation—time curves in Figs. 3 and 4 which show the influence of different proportions of gelatine in the coagulating mixture. This might be ascribed either to the higher concentration of the coagulator used, or to the presence of the protector, or what is more probable, to both these factors.

FIG. 4.

The colloid was protected by 0.025% (curve 11) and 0.059% gelatine (curve 14—15). The coagulator conc. for curves 11, 14 and 15 were N/11.7, N/13.3 and N/10-KCl respectively.

FIG. 5.

Coagulation of gelatine solution, 0.1% for curves 16 and 17 and 0.05% for curve 18. Coagulator conc. for curves 16–18 were $N/2$, N , and $N/2$ -KCl respectively.

Two features of some interest are noticeable from curves in Figs. 1–5. The first is the almost invariable initial diminution of viscosity and second, the fact that in practically no case does the viscosity rise smoothly during the progress of coagulation. Both these facts militate against the use of viscosity as a quantitative measure of coagulation at any rate with low concentrations of the coagulator. Accuracy of the experimental arrangement used here, and the number of observations taken indicate that the non-uniformities and breaks on these curves can not be ascribed to experimental error. In our opinion, these suggest that coagulation, especially in the *slow region*, is a complex process in which the particles undergo a succession of changes, presumably both as to their size and nature. This would appear to be the main reason for the breakdown of the Smoluchowski's theory (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1917, 92, 129), or its simple extension based on the assumption that coagulation is but a continued coalescence of particles discharged initially completely, or partially.

It is probable, for instance, starting with a certain number of primaries mixed with the electrolyte, the formation of agglomerates through successive coalescence might prevail as the main process producing the viscosity change in a certain sense during the given period. Now, after this period the agglomerates might suffer a breakdown due (i) to instability induced as a result of the attainment of a certain size and structure during the coalescence, or (ii) by the action of similarly charged ions. This will produce a viscosity change in a direction opposite to what happened just previously.

Observed over a prolonged time, the operation of the two sets of factors mentioned above will produce mainly fluctuations on the coagulation—time curve. Evidence was cited in a previous paper (Joshi and Joga Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 273) that viscosity is particularly susceptible to even such alterations in a colloid as might be missed for example by the familiar turbidity method of observing coagulation. In coagulations due to higher concentrations of the coagulator, velocity of the change is so great that the coalescence process passing through the formation of agglomerates ends only with precipitation which ordinarily is an irreversible process. It follows, therefore, that fluctuations in the sense described above are to be anticipated only when dilute solutions of the coagulator are employed. A comparison of curves 6, 7 in Fig. 2, curves 14, 15 in Fig. 4, and 16, 17, 18 in Fig. 5 with the rest illustrates clearly the above possibility. It might be observed incidentally that the above suggestion, regarding the nature of possible conditions under which there is no net advance in the coagulation, might also explain results in connection with the 'Bodländer's limit.'

FIG. 6.

The initial diminution of viscosity observed in practically all the coagulations varies in the range from 0.7 to 1.9% of the initial viscosity of the colloid (*cf.* Tables I--V). It is interesting to note that the time reckoned from the start of coagulation up to the occurrence of this fall of viscosity is roughly constant for a given series of coagulations. It is also of interest to note from Fig. 6 that the interval during which viscosity remains at, or below the first *minimum*, rises rapidly with the dilution of the coagulator, and would

tend to be infinitely large for very low dilutions, presumably corresponding to the 'Bodländer's limit' for the colloid used. This initial diminution must be regarded as distinctive of at least one of the stages constituting the progress of coagulation at any rate in the *slow region*. Whilst it has not been possible so far to obtain a complete elucidation of this phenomenon, it is important to mention that this initial fall of viscosity, and the occurrence of fluctuations, (the latter under conditions mentioned in the above discussion, the coagulation being measured by different means) have been found to be features of almost universal occurrence in diverse coagulating systems in *slow region*. A discussion of these results is reserved for a later communication.

SUMMARY.

Slow coagulations of simple arsenious sulphide sols and when protected by different amounts of gelatine, as well as of pure gelatine sols of different strengths, due to potassium chloride solutions in the range N to $N/20$ have been examined by measuring the viscosity of the coagulating system. The coagulation—time curves show some or all of the following three characteristics: (i) The viscosity shows an initial diminution (up to a maximum of about 1.9%), the corresponding time being roughly constant in a given series of coagulations. (ii) The next section of the curve rises slowly at first and then rapidly, indicative of *autocatalysis*. (iii) The last feature is absent for high as well as for very low concentrations of the coagulator. Under the last factor, subsequent to (i) the coagulation—time curves show only periodic fluctuations without an appreciable net increase of viscosity, for which an explanation has been suggested.